

Supplementary materials, tables, and figures for Long-acting Growth Hormone for Pediatric Growth Hormone Deficiency by Albers N, Cadarette S, Feakins B, et al.

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Supplementary network meta-analysis methods

Dichotomous outcomes were evaluated by extracting the number of patients with the event and the number of patients in each treatment arm. Continuous outcomes were determined by extracting the change from baseline in each study arm, if available, or by calculating it as the difference between the baseline score and the score at 52 weeks. The only exception was the annualized height velocity outcome, where only the measurements at 52 weeks were used.

Where standard deviations (SDs) were not available for the raw values at either baseline or follow-up, they were calculated from associated standard errors (SEs) and the population sample size (n). Where change from baseline SEs were not available, these were calculated from the baseline (BL) and follow-up (FU) SDs using the following formula:

$$\circ \quad SD_{CFB} = \sqrt{SD_{BL}^2 + SD_{FU}^2 - (2 \times r \times SD_{BL} \times SD_{FU})}$$

The correlation between baseline and follow-up measures (r) was estimated from the complete case data. Where baseline, follow-up, or change from baseline SDs were not available (and could not be calculated), they were imputed using the weighted mean of the SDs, per outcome type.^{1,2}

Monte Carlo Markov chains were used to calculate posterior distributions for parameters of interest. These distributions were derived from likelihood functions based on data and prior probabilities and selected according to the United Kingdom's National Institute for Health and Care Excellence recommendations.³

The analysis utilized a model within a Bayesian framework that included parameters, a likelihood distribution, and prior distributions. ³ For binary outcomes, a network meta-analysis was conducted using a regression model with binomial likelihood and logit link function. Non-informative priors were used to parametrize the study-specific intercepts ($\mathcal{N}(0,100)$) and treatment effect ($\mathcal{N}(0,10)$). Relative treatment effects were expressed as odds ratios. For continuous outcomes, a normal likelihood and identity link function were used. Priors for continuous outcome data were also parametrized as $\mathcal{N}(0,100)$ for the study-specific intercepts and $\mathcal{N}(0,10)$ for the treatment effects. Relative treatment effects were reported as mean differences. As each contrast was described by only a single trial in the base case, only fixed-effect models were calculated.

Model parameter estimation involved a Markov Chain Monte Carlo algorithm implemented in the *multinma* R package. All analyses were performed using R version 4.3.2 (“Eye Holes”) and *multinma* version 0.5.1.

Tables and figures

Supplementary Table 1. Search strings in MEDLINE and Embase (via Ovid)

#	Query	Results from 10 Aug 2023
1	(exp adolescent/ or exp child/ or exp infant/ or (infant disease* or childhood disease*).ti,ab,kf. or (adolescen* or babies or baby or boy? or boyfriend or boyhood or girlfriend or girlhood or child* or girl? or infan* or juvenil* or kid? or minors or minors* or neonat* or neo-nat* or newborn* or new-born* or paediatric* or peadiatric* or pediatric* or perinat* or preschool* or puber* or pubescen* or school* or teen* or toddler? or underage? or under-age? or youth*).ti,ab,kf. or (pediatric* or paediatric* or infan* or child* or adolescen* or young).jn,jw. or (pediatric* or paediatric* or infan* or child* or adolescen* or young).in.) use medall	5,715,708
2	(exp *adolescent/ or exp *child/ or exp *infant/ or (infant disease* or childhood disease*).ti,kf. or (adolescen* or babies or baby or boy? or boyfriend or boyhood or girlfriend or girlhood or child* or girl? or infan* or juvenil* or kid? or minors or minors* or neonat* or neo-nat* or newborn* or new-born* or paediatric* or peadiatric* or pediatric* or perinat* or preschool* or puber* or pubescen* or school* or teen* or toddler? or underage? or under-age? or youth*).ti,kf. or (pediatric* or paediatric* or infan* or child* or adolescen* or young).jn,jw. or (pediatric* or paediatric* or infan* or child* or adolescen* or young).in.) use oomezd	3,908,478
3	1 or 2	9,624,186
4	exp growth hormone deficiency/ use oomezd	14,875

#	Query	Results from 10 Aug 2023
5	exp pituitary dwarfism/ use oomezd	794
6	exp Dwarfism, Pituitary/ use medall	2,545
7	Growth Disorders/ use medall	18,721
8	(growth hormone or growth-hormone or human growth hormone or somatatro* or somatropin or growth hormone deficiency or growth hormone disorder or growth hormone disease or growth hormone condition or growth hormone insufficiency or GH deficiency or pituitary dwarf* or ateliotic dwarf* or neurosecretory dysfunction).mp.	187,093
9	or/4-8	201,137
10	(SKYTROFA or Lonapegsomatropin or Sogroya or Somapacitan or NGENLA or Somatrogon or MOD-4023 or Eftansomatropin or GX-H9 or Jintrolong or PEG-rhGH or Eutropin plus or somatropin SR).mp.	311
11	(somatropin or Genotropin or Humatrope or Norditropin or NutropinAQ or Nutropin AQ or Omnitrope or Saizen or Zomacton or Zorbktiv or Maxomat).mp.	3,647
12	or/10-11	3,863
13	3 and 9 and 12	1,773
14	Clinical trial/	1,606,972
15	exp Randomized controlled trial/	1,378,905
16	Randomization/ use oomezd	98,108
17	Prospective study/ use oomezd	870,760
18	Single blind procedure/ use oomezd	51,347
19	Double blind procedure/ use oomezd	209,432
20	Crossover procedure/ use oomezd	74,962
21	Placebo/ use oomezd	400,750
22	Random allocation/ use medall	106,954
23	Double blind method/ use medall	175,883
24	Single blind method/ use medall	32,858
25	Controlled clinical trial/ use oomezd	470,730
26	Placebos/ use medall	35,932
27	(allocated adj2 random).ti,ab.	1,785
28	Placebo\$.ti,ab.	613,901
29	(clinic\$ adj trial\$1).ti,ab.	1,172,139
30	((singl\$ or doubl\$ or treb\$ or tripl\$) adj (blind\$3 or mask\$3)).ti,ab.	478,657
31	rct.ti,ab.	85,329
32	Randomi?ed controlled trial\$.ti,ab.	572,686
33	(random* or factorial* or crossover* or (cross adj over*) or placebo* or assign* or allocat* or volunteer*).ti,ab.	4,831,155
34	((singl* or doubl*) adj2 blind*).ti,ab.	468,181
35	(crossover procedure or double-blind procedure or randomized controlled trial or single-blind procedure).ti,ab.	243,730
36	Clinical study/	169,098
37	case control study/	534,769

#	Query	Results from 10 Aug 2023
38	Family study/	25,725
39	Longitudinal study/	361,705
40	Retrospective study/	2,607,691
41	Prospective study/	1,535,749
42	Cohort analysis/	1,364,346
43	(Cohort adj1 (study or studies)).tw.	826,106
44	(Case control adj1 (study or studies)).tw.	296,981
45	((follow up or follow-up) adj1 (study or studies)).tw.	135,727
46	(observational adj1 (study or studies)).tw.	416,399
47	(epidemiologic\$ adj1 (study or studies)).tw.	218,604
48	((cross sectional or cross-sectional) adj1 (study or studies)).tw.	601,460
49	register/	127,012
50	registries/	186,035
51	(register\$ or registry or registries\$.ti,ab.	1,037,540
52	(single arm or single-arm).mp. [mp=ti, ab, hw, tn, ot, dm, mf, dv, kf, fx, dq, bt, nm, ox, px, rx, an, ui, sy, ux, mx]	40,987
53	or/14-52	12,967,191
54	13 and 53	1,036
55	exp animals/	57,097,175
56	exp human/	46,827,136
57	55 not 56	10,270,039
58	(letter or editorial or comment\$ or note or case report).pt.	5,193,967
59	case study/ or letter/ or editorial/ or case report/	8,698,905
60	or/57-59	20,071,009
61	54 not 60	1,004
62	systematic review.pt.	235,165
63	systematic review.ti.	480,794
64	or/62-63	547,589
65	review.pt.	6,299,488
66	65 not 64	6,018,600
67	61 not 66	960
68	conference abstract.pt.	4,847,424
69	limit 68 to yr="1974 - 2020"	4,143,778
70	67 not 69	814
71	remove duplicates from 70	682

Supplementary Table 2. Trials excluded from analysis during feasibility assessment

Trial	Reference	Reason for exclusion
Chatelain 2017⁴	Chatelain P, et al. A randomized phase 2 study of long-acting transcon GH vs daily GH in childhood GH deficiency. <i>J Clin Endocrinol Metab.</i> 2017;102(5):1673-1682.	Unapproved dose of LAGH
Du 2022⁵	Du H, et al. Efficacy and safety of long-acting PEGylated recombinant human growth hormone (Jintrolong) for patients with growth hormone deficiency. <i>J Pediatr Endocrinol Metab.</i> 2022;35(4):511-517.	Unapproved dose of LAGH ^a
Liang 2022⁶	Liang Y, et al. Pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties of a novel once-weekly PEGylated recombinant human growth hormone for children with growth hormone deficiency. <i>Front Endocrinol (Lausanne).</i> 2022;13:922304.	Only 1 treatment arm of interest
Luo 2017 (phase 2)⁷ Luo 2017 (phase 3)⁷	Luo X, et al. Long-acting PEGylated recombinant human growth hormone (Jintrolong) for children with growth hormone deficiency: Phase II and phase III multicenter, randomized studies. <i>Eur J Endocrinol.</i> 2017;177(2):195-205.	No 52-week timepoint
Péter 2012⁸	Péter F, et al. Three-year efficacy and safety of LB03002, a once-weekly sustained-release growth hormone preparation, in prepubertal children with GHD. <i>J Clin Endocrinol Metab.</i> 2012;97(2):400-407.	No 52-week timepoint
REAL 3⁹	Savendahl L, et al. Once-weekly somapacitan vs daily GH in children with GH deficiency: Results from a randomized phase 2 trial. <i>J Clin Endocrinol Metab.</i> 2020;105(4):e1847-e1861.	Small sample size (dose-finding study)
Silverman 2002¹⁰	Silverman BL, et al. A long-acting human growth hormone (Nutropin Depot): Efficacy and safety following two years of treatment in children with growth hormone deficiency. <i>J Pediatr Endocrinol Metab.</i> 2002;(15 Suppl 2):715-722.	Small sample size (dose-finding study)
Zelinska 2017¹¹	Zelinska N, et al. Long-acting C-terminal peptide-modified hGH (MOD-4023): Results of a safety and dose-finding study in GHD children. <i>J Clin Endocrinol Metab.</i> 2017;102(5):1578-1587.	Unapproved dose of LAGH ^b

Key: GH – growth hormone; GHD – growth hormone deficiency; hGH – human growth hormone; LAGH – long-acting growth hormone.

^a One arm of interest was of an approved dose of Jintrolong; however, the comparator arm dose was unapproved.

^b Trial evaluated once-monthly vs. twice-monthly dosing. Additionally, the trial did not connect in a network and the LAGH assessed was discontinued.

Supplementary Table 3. Comparison of baseline and intervention characteristics for sensitivity analysis trials vs. base case trials

Characteristic	Khadilkar 2014 ¹² (sensitivity analysis 1)	Horikawa 2022 ¹³ (sensitivity analysis 2)
Sex	Greater proportion of female participants vs. base case trials	Greater proportion of female participants vs. base case trials
Ethnicity	NR	Greater proportion of Asian participants (100%)
Age	Similar to base case trials	Similar; did extend the range of mean ages across included trials to 2.5 years
Bone age	NR	Consistent with only base case trial (heiGHT) reporting bone age
Height and weight	Similar to REAL 4	NR
Height SDS and height velocity SDS	Higher than base case trials	Similar to base case trials

IGF-1 SDS	Higher than the range seen in the base case trials; twice the magnitude of the next highest trial (-4.3 vs. -2.1)	Lower than the range seen in the base case trials
Disease etiology	Similar proportion of patients with idiopathic and organic GHD compared to base case trials Higher proportion of patients with multiple pituitary hormone deficiencies than heiGHt	NR
Peak GH stimulation	Less than half the magnitude of the next lowest trial from the base case analysis (2.1 vs. 4.6)	NR
Dose of daily somatropin	Similar to base case trials	Lower than base case trials

Key: GH – growth hormone; GHD – growth hormone deficiency; IGF-1 – insulin-like growth factor-1; NR – not reported; SDS – standard deviation score.

Supplementary Figure 1. Summary of the quality critical appraisal of included studies

Key: ITT – intention-to-treat.

Horikawa 2022 was high-risk for question 3; all trials were high-risk for question 4.

Q1: Was the method used to generate random allocations adequate? **Q2:** Was the allocation adequately concealed? **Q3:** Were the groups similar at the outset of the study in terms of prognostic factors (eg, severity of disease?) **Q4:** Were the care providers, participants, and outcome assessors blind to treatment allocation? **Q5:** Were there any unexpected imbalances in drop-outs between groups? If so, were they explained or adjusted for? **Q6:** Is there any evidence to suggest that the authors measured more outcomes than they reported? **Q7:** Did the analysis include an intention-to-treat analysis? If so, was this appropriate and were appropriate methods used to account for missing data?

Supplementary Table 4. Outcomes excluded from analysis

Efficacy		Safety	
Outcome	Reason	Outcome	Reason
Compliance/adherence	Data collection methods differ and raw values for rate calculations are not reported	Total AEs/TEAEs	Differences in definitions across trials
BMI and BMI SDS	Less than 3 trial results available for comparison	Injection-site reactions	Differences in definitions across trials
Pubertal transition	Less than 3 trial results available for comparison	Neutralizing anti-hGH antibodies	Insufficient data (1 trial reported participants experiencing an event)
Height velocity SDS	Less than 3 trial results available for comparison	Non-neutralizing anti-hGH antibodies	Differences in definitions across trials
Fractures	No data available	Dose reductions/temporary discontinuations due to AEs	Differences in definitions across trials
		Discontinuations due to AEs	Insufficient data (only 2 events reported across all trials)

Key: AE – adverse event; BMI – body mass index; hGH – human growth hormone; SDS – standard deviation score; TEAE – treatment-emergent adverse event.

Supplementary Table 5. Annualized height velocity probability of cumulative ranking, base case

Treatment	Probability of cumulative ranking				SUCRA
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	
Daily somatropin	0.00	0.16	0.94	1.00	37%
Somapacitan	0.00	0.03	0.09	1.00	4%
Somatrogon	0.12	0.82	0.97	1.00	64%
Lonapegsomatropin	0.88	0.99	1.00	1.00	96%

Key: SUCRA – surface under the cumulative ranking curve.

Supplementary Table 6. Height SDS probability of cumulative ranking, base case

Treatment	Probability of cumulative ranking				SUCRA
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	
Daily somatropin	0.00	0.25	0.96	1.00	40%
Somapacitan	0.00	0.02	0.07	1.00	3%
Somatrogon	0.18	0.75	0.97	1.00	63%
Lonapegsomatropin	0.82	0.99	1.00	1.00	93%

Key: SDS – standard deviation score; SUCRA – surface under the cumulative ranking curve.

Supplementary Table 7. IGF-1 SDS probability of cumulative ranking, base case

Treatment	Probability of cumulative ranking				SUCRA
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	
Daily somatropin	0.00	0.00	0.43	1.00	14%
Somapacitan	0.00	0.00	0.57	1.00	19%
Somatrogon	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	100%
Lonapegsomatropin	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	67%

Key: IGF-1 – insulin-like growth factor 1; SDS – standard deviation score; SUCRA – surface under the cumulative ranking curve.

Supplementary Table 8. Bone age-to-chronological age probability of cumulative ranking, base case

Treatment	Probability of cumulative ranking				SUCRA
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	
Daily somatropin	0.35	0.84	0.99	1.00	72%
Somapacitan	0.07	0.17	0.41	1.00	22%
Somatrogon	0.13	0.35	0.75	1.00	41%
Lonapegsomatropin	0.46	0.64	0.85	1.00	62%

Key: SUCRA – surface under the cumulative ranking curve.

Supplementary Table 9. Total SAEs probability of cumulative ranking, base case

Treatment	Probability of cumulative ranking				SUCRA
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	
Daily somatropin	0.18	0.67	0.95	1.00	60%
Somapacitan	0.10	0.29	0.60	1.00	33%
Somatrogon	0.13	0.33	0.61	1.00	36%
Lonapegsomatropin	0.59	0.71	0.83	1.00	71%

Key: SAE – serious adverse event; SUCRA – surface under the cumulative ranking curve.

Supplementary Figure 2. Forest plot of annualized height velocity at 52 weeks: Sensitivity analysis 1

Sensitivity analysis 1, including the Khadilkar 2014 trial, added a direct comparison between LB03002 and daily somatropin. Compared with LB03002, lonapegsomatropin had a significantly higher follow-up annualized height velocity at week 52. Orange box indicates significant results.

Key: CrI – credible interval; yr – year.

Supplementary Figure 3. Forest plot of height SDS change from baseline: Sensitivity analysis 1

Sensitivity analysis 1, including the Khadilkar 2014 trial, added a direct comparison between LB03002 and daily somatropin. Orange box indicates significant results.

Key: CrI – credible interval; SDS – standard deviation score.

Supplementary Figure 4. Forest plot of IGF-1 SDS change from baseline: Sensitivity analysis 1

Sensitivity analysis 1, including the Khadilkar 2014 trial, added a direct comparison between LB03002 and daily somatropin. Compared with LB03002, somatrogon had a significantly higher change from baseline in average IGF-1 SDS. Orange box indicates significant results.

Key: CrI – credible interval; IGF-1 – insulin-like growth factor-1; SDS – standard deviation score.

Supplementary Figure 5. Forest plot of bone age-to-chronological age ratio change from baseline: Sensitivity analysis 1

Sensitivity analysis 1, including the Khadilkar 2014 trial, added a direct comparison between LB03002 and daily somatotropin. LB03002 showed a significantly higher change from baseline in bone age-to-chronological age ratio than somapacitan. Orange box indicates significant results.

Key: CrI – credible interval.

Supplementary Figure 6. Forest plot of total SAEs: Sensitivity analysis 1

Sensitivity analysis 1, including the Khadilkar 2014 trial, added a direct comparison between LB03002 and daily somatropin. Orange box indicates significant results.

Key: CrI – credible interval; OR – odds ratio; SAE – serious adverse event.

Supplementary Figure 7. Forest plot of annualized height velocity at 52 weeks: Sensitivity analysis 2

Sensitivity analysis 2, including the Horikawa 2022 trial, provided an additional data source for the direct comparison of somatrogon to daily somatropin. In this analysis, the comparisons for somatrogon vs. somapacitan and somatrogon vs. daily somatropin showed a significantly higher annualized height velocity at 52 weeks, whereas in the base case analysis, these comparisons only showed numerical differences. Orange box indicates significant results.

Key: cm – centimeter; CrI – credible interval; yr – year.

Supplementary Figure 8. Forest plot of height SDS change from baseline: Sensitivity analysis 2

Sensitivity analysis 2, including the Horikawa 2022 trial, provided an additional data source for the direct comparison of somatrogon to daily somatropin. In this analysis, the comparisons for somatrogon vs. somapacitan and somatrogon vs. daily somatropin showed a significantly larger change from baseline in height SDS, whereas in the base case analysis, these comparisons only showed numerical differences. Orange box indicates significant results.

Key: CrI – credible interval; SDS – standard deviation score.

Supplementary Figure 9. Forest plot of IGF-1 SDS change from baseline: Sensitivity analysis 2

Sensitivity analysis 2, including the Horikawa 2022 trial, provided an additional data source for the direct comparison of somatrogon to daily somatropin. Orange box indicates significant results.

Key: CrI – credible interval; IGF-1 – insulin-like growth factor-1; SDS – standard deviation score.

Supplementary Figure 10. Forest plot of bone age-to-chronological age ratio change from baseline: Sensitivity analysis 2

Sensitivity analysis 2, including the Horikawa 2022 trial, provided an additional data source for the direct comparison of somatrogon to daily somatropin. Orange box indicates significant results.

Key: CrI – credible interval.

Supplementary Figure 11. Forest plot of total SAEs: Sensitivity analysis 2

Sensitivity analysis 2, including the Horikawa 2022 trial, provided an additional data source for the direct comparison of somatrogon to daily somatropin. Orange box indicates significant results.

Key: CrI – credible interval; OR – odds ratio; SAE – serious adverse event.

Supplementary Table 10. Annualized height velocity probability of cumulative ranking, sensitivity analysis 1

Treatment	Probability of cumulative ranking					SUCRA
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Fifth	
Daily somatropin	0.00	0.12	0.77	0.99	1.00	47%
LB03002	0.01	0.09	0.23	0.68	1.00	25%
Somapacitan	0.00	0.03	0.08	0.35	1.00	11%
Somatrogon	0.12	0.77	0.92	0.99	1.00	70%
Lonapegsomatropin	0.87	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	96%

Key: SUCRA – surface under the cumulative ranking curve.

Supplementary Table 11. Height SDS probability of cumulative ranking, sensitivity analysis 1

Treatment	Probability of cumulative ranking					SUCRA
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Fifth	
Daily somatropin	0.00	0.18	0.76	0.99	1.00	48%
LB03002	0.04	0.16	0.31	0.77	1.00	32%
Somapacitan	0.00	0.02	0.05	0.26	1.00	8%

SLR and NMA of LAGH for pGHD

Somatrogon	0.16	0.67	0.88	0.98	1.00	67%
Lonapegsomatropin	0.79	0.97	0.99	1.00	1.00	94%

Key: SDS – standard deviation score; SUCRA – surface under the cumulative ranking curve.

Supplementary Table 12. IGF-1 SDS probability of cumulative ranking, sensitivity analysis 1

Treatment	Probability of cumulative ranking					SUCRA
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Fifth	
Daily somatotropin	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.49	1.00	13%
LB03002	0.00	0.03	0.82	0.93	1.00	44%
Somapacitan	0.00	0.00	0.14	0.58	1.00	18%
Somatrogon	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	100%
Lonapegsomatropin	0.00	0.97	1.00	1.00	1.00	74%

Key: IGF-1 – insulin-like growth factor-1; SDS – standard deviation score; SUCRA – surface under the cumulative ranking curve.

Supplementary Table 13. Bone age-to-chronological age ratio probability of cumulative ranking, sensitivity analysis 1

Treatment	Probability of cumulative ranking					SUCRA
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Fifth	
Daily somatotropin	0.01	0.38	0.84	0.99	1.00	56%
LB03002	0.83	0.95	0.98	0.99	1.00	94%
Somapacitan	0.01	0.07	0.17	0.41	1.00	17%
Somatrogon	0.02	0.14	0.36	0.76	1.00	32%
Lonapegsomatropin	0.12	0.46	0.64	0.85	1.00	52%

Key: SUCRA – surface under the cumulative ranking curve.

Supplementary Table 14. Total SAEs probability of cumulative ranking, sensitivity analysis 1

Treatment	Probability of cumulative ranking					SUCRA
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Fifth	
Daily somatotropin	0.09	0.42	0.81	0.98	1.00	57%
LB03002	0.25	0.49	0.65	0.84	1.00	56%
Somapacitan	0.07	0.20	0.38	0.66	1.00	33%
Somatrogon	0.09	0.24	0.42	0.67	1.00	36%
Lonapegsomatropin	0.50	0.65	0.74	0.85	1.00	68%

Key: SAE – serious adverse event; SUCRA – surface under the cumulative ranking curve.

Supplementary Table 15. Annualized height velocity probability of cumulative ranking, sensitivity analysis 2

Treatment	Probability of cumulative ranking				SUCRA
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	
Daily somatotropin	0.00	0.01	0.93	1.00	31%

SLR and NMA of LAGH for pGHD

Somapacitan	0.00	0.00	0.08	1.00	3%
Somatrogon	0.56	1.00	1.00	1.00	85%
Lonapegsomatropin	0.44	0.99	1.00	1.00	81%

Key: SUCRA – surface under the cumulative ranking curve.

Supplementary Table 16. Height SDS probability of cumulative ranking, sensitivity analysis 2

Treatment	Probability of cumulative ranking				SUCRA
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	
Daily somatropin	0.00	0.01	0.95	1.00	32%
Somapacitan	0.00	0.01	0.05	1.00	2%
Somatrogon	0.73	1.00	1.00	1.00	91%
Lonapegsomatropin	0.27	0.98	1.00	1.00	75%

Key: SDS – standard deviation score; SUCRA – surface under the cumulative ranking curve.

Supplementary Table 17. IGF-1 SDS probability of cumulative ranking, sensitivity analysis 2

Treatment	Probability of cumulative ranking				SUCRA
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	
Daily somatropin	0.00	0.00	0.43	1.00	14%
Somapacitan	0.00	0.00	0.57	1.00	19%
Somatrogon	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	100%
Lonapegsomatropin	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	67%

Key: IGF-1 – insulin-like growth factor-1; SDS – standard deviation score; SUCRA – surface under the cumulative ranking curve.

Supplementary Table 18. Bone age-to-chronological age ratio probability of cumulative ranking, sensitivity analysis 2

Treatment	Probability of cumulative ranking				SUCRA
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	
Daily somatropin	0.25	0.73	0.98	1.00	65%
Somapacitan	0.06	0.13	0.32	1.00	17%
Somatrogon	0.27	0.57	0.89	1.00	58%
Lonapegsomatropin	0.42	0.57	0.82	1.00	60%

Key: SUCRA – surface under the cumulative ranking curve.

Supplementary Table 19. Total SAEs probability of cumulative ranking, sensitivity analysis 2

Treatment	Probability of cumulative ranking				SUCRA
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	
Daily somatropin	0.17	0.64	0.95	1.00	59%
Somapacitan	0.10	0.27	0.53	1.00	30%
Somatrogon	0.14	0.39	0.72	1.00	42%
Lonapegsomatropin	0.59	0.69	0.81	1.00	70%

Key: SAE – serious adverse event; SUCRA – surface under the cumulative ranking curve.

References

1. Follmann D, Elliott P, Suh I, Cutler J. Variance imputation for overviews of clinical trials with continuous response. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 1992;45(7):769-773.
2. Abrams KR, Gillies CL, Lambert PC. Meta-analysis of heterogeneously reported trials assessing change from baseline. *Stat Med*. 2005;24(24):3823-3844.
3. Dias S, Welton NJ, Sutton AJ, Ades AE. NICE DSU Technical Support Document 2: A generalised linear modelling framework for pairwise and network meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials. Report by the Decision Support Unit. Accessed September 3, 2023. <https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2022-02/TSD2-General-meta-analysiscorrected-2Sep2016v2.pdf>
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